

Kinetic Investigation on the Complex Formation of Nickel(II) with *N*-Benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine

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Stopped-flow spectrophotometric investigation on the complex formation of Ni^{2+} with *N*-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine indicated the formation of NiL and NiL_2^{2-} complexes in two consecutive steps involving pre-equilibrium. Successive pre-equilibrium constants (K' , 168.3 mol^{-1} ; K'' , 320.5 mol^{-1}) and successive formation rate constants (k_1 , 30.3 s^{-1} ; k_2 , 6.3 s^{-1}) have been determined at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in aqueous solution at a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3), and discussed on the basis of modes of bonding of the ligand, π -electron delocalisation in the metal-ligand bonds.

EQUILIBRIUM study¹⁻³ of the complex formation of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} with the ligand *N*-benzenesulphonyl-L-cysteine, $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH(COOH)CH_2SH$ (hereafter, NBSC or H_2L) indicated stepwise formation of successive complexes, viz. ML , ML_2^{2-} , $M(H_{-1}L)(L)^{2-}$ and $M(H_{-1}L)_2^{4-}$ through bidentate (N, S) chelation of the metal ions ($M(II) = Co^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) by the ligand species. For Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} systems, the observed ratio ($K_{ML}^M : K_{ML_2}^M$) of successive formation constants were found to be less than the statistically expected values (Table 1). In the case of Ni^{2+} complexes an

arise due to faster rate of formation and/or slower rate of dissociation of the complex ML_2 . It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to investigate the formation of NiL and NiL_2^{2-} complexes by stopped-flow spectrophotometry which is suitable for studying such moderately fast reactions as commonly observed with Ni^{2+} .

Experimental

Stock solution of 0.01 M nickel(II) nitrate was prepared by dissolving $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (A.R.) in water adding sufficient nitric acid to suppress hydrolysis of $Ni(aq.)^{2+}$ ions, and standardised by the reported procedure³. A given volume of standard 0.01 M solution of the monosodium salt, $C_6H_5SO_2NHCH(COONa)CH_2SH$, of NBSC^{1,5} was prepared by mixing NBSC with the required quantity of carbonate-free NaOH solution. All the other reagents were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled CO_2 -free water was used for making the solutions.

A SYSTRONICS 335 digital pH meter, (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) having a special glass electrode in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode was used for pH measurements. Electronic spectra of the metal-ligand mixtures at different pH were recorded with a Hilgar UVISPEK spectrophotometer. Absorbance vs time data were recorded with a SF-3A Canterbury Hi-Tech stopped-flow spectrophotometer equipped with a DL-901 transient recorder and an oscilloscope.

Procedure: Electronic spectra of solutions containing 0.001 M Ni^{2+} in the presence of 0.005 M NBSC adjusted to pH 7–9.5 corresponding to the maximum formation of the NiL_2^{2-} complex^{3,4} were recorded. The spectra was analogous to that of Ni^{2+} in low-spin systems. Absorption maxima at 430 nm was used in the stopped-flow experiment.

TABLE 1—SUCCESSIVE STABILITY CONSTANTS¹⁻⁴ OF Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} AND Zn^{2+} COMPLEXES WITH NBSC AT $30 \pm 1^\circ$ IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS ETHANOL MEDIUM HAVING A CONSTANT IONIC STRENGTH $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3)

M	$\log K_{ML}^M$	$\log K_{ML_2}^M$	$\log (K_{ML}^M / K_{ML_2}^M)^*$
Co^{2+}	6.64	6.09	+0.55
Ni	6.30	6.61	-0.31
Zn^{2+}	7.95	7.35	+0.60

*Statistically expected $\log (K_{ML}^M / K_{ML_2}^M)$ value = +0.68 for octahedral complexes.

unusual order, $K_{ML}^M < K_{ML_2}^M$ was observed. Such unusually higher values of the second step formation constant, $K_{ML_2}^M$, over the first step formation constant, K_{ML}^M , was attributed to the enhancement of electronegativity of the metal ion as a consequence of back donation in the M–S (thiol) bonds (where, $M = Co, Ni$) in the ML complexes. $K_{ML}^M : K_{ML_2}^M$ value for the Zn^{2+} -NBSC complexes, where π -electron delocalisation was not possible, were close to the statistically expected values. Kinetically such unusual order of successive formation constants (as in the case of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} complexes) may

Equal volumes of pre-thermostated (30±0.1°) aqueous solutions of nickel(II) nitrate (0.001–0.002 M) and monosodium salt of NBSC (0.01–0.05 M), adjusted to required ionic strengths, were quickly mixed in the thermostated cell housing of the stopped-flow spectrophotometer and the increase in the optical density (A) for 430 nm as a function of time (t) was displayed on the oscilloscope screen.

Equal volumes of the same solutions of the metal and ligand were mixed and pH values of the resulting mixtures were measured at the experimental temperature by usual procedure¹⁻³.

Results and Discussion

Time absorbance data for the reaction of Ni²⁺ with NBSC at different pH and at different concentrations of NBSC are presented in Fig. 1 and 2,

Fig. 1

Fig 2

Fig. 1. Time absorbance data (t, A) for the reaction of Ni²⁺ with NBSC at pH 9.40 at different concentration of NBSC kept in large excess.

Fig. 2. Time absorbance data (t, A) for the reaction of Ni²⁺ with NBSC in the presence of constant large excess of NBSC at different pH.

respectively. [NBSC] : [Ni²⁺] ratio was always kept sufficiently large (≥ 20) so as to get time absorbance data (t, A) suitable for the evaluation of pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) for the complex formation reaction. Graphical analysis^{6,7} of the (t, A) data indicated the existence of two consecutive reaction steps, each involving pre-equilibrium, ultimately leading to the formation a Ni²⁺ : 2NBSC complex. The observed rate constants, (k_{obs})₁ and (k_{obs})₂ for the successive formation steps were evaluated (Table 2). Both (k_{obs})₁ and (k_{obs})₂ were found to be independent of pH of the solution in

TABLE 2—(k_{obs})₁, (k_{obs})₂, K', K'', k₁ AND k₂ VALUES FOR THE REACTION OF Ni²⁺ WITH NBSC IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 30±0.1° AT CONSTANT IONIC STRENGTH μ = 0.1 M (NaNO₃)

(a) pH variation : [Ni ²⁺] = 0.001 M, [NBSC] = 0.04 M							
pH	7.07	7.69	7.77	8.07	9.10	9.28	9.40
(k _{obs}) ₁ (s ⁻¹)	27.1	26.5	26.5	26.1	27.1	26.5	27.3
(b) Ligand variation : [Ni ²⁺] = 0.001 M, pH = 9.40 ± 0.02							
[NBSC](M)	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05		
(k _{obs}) ₁ (s ⁻¹)	18.9	23.9	25.3	26.5	27.6		
(k _{obs}) ₂ (s ⁻¹)	4.8	5.5	5.6	5.8	5.9		
(c) Rate constants (k ₁ , k ₂) and pre-equilibrium constants : (K', K'')							
k ₁ (s ⁻¹)		k ₂ (s ⁻¹)		K' (mol ⁻¹)		K'' (mol ⁻¹)	
30.3		6.3		168.5		320.3	

the experimental pH range (7–9.5) in the presence of a constant large excess of the ligand. On the other hand, variation of (k_{obs}) values with ligand concentration [NBSC] at fixed pH values could be expressed by a reciprocal relations of the type (1)

$$1/(k_{obs}) = A' + B'/[NBSC] \quad (1)$$

where, (k_{obs}) stands for (k_{obs})₁ or (k_{obs})₂ as the case may be and A' and B' are constants. Such dependence of the observed rate constants with concentration of the ligand, when kept 10–20 times in excess over that of the metal ion, indicated the existence of pre-equilibrium steps⁶. The ligand NBSC (H₂L) remains exclusively in the LH⁻ form in the experimental pH range (7–9.5) (as pK_{a1}^H, 3.50; pK_{a2}^H, 10.42 at 30±0.1°). Under the experimental condition, [LH⁻] >> [OH⁻]. It was, therefore, unlikely for the OH⁻ ion to appear as a competitor of the LH⁻ ion to bind the Ni²⁺ ion in the complexation processes. Complex formation of Ni²⁺ with NBSC was, therefore, assumed to have taken place as follows (charge were dropped for clarity),

First step :

Second step :

where, K' and K'' are the successive pre-equilibrium constants¹¹ and k₁ and k₂ are the rate constants for the respective steps. Observed rate constants for the successive steps (2) and (3) were^{6,10} therefore,

$$(k_{obs})_1 = K'k_1 [NBSC]/(1 + K'[NBSC]) \quad (4)$$

$$(k_{obs})_2 = K''k_2 [NBSC]/(1 + K''[NBSC]) \quad (5)$$

The constants K', K'', k₁ and k₂ were graphically evaluated (Fig. 3) employing the relations (6) and (7)

$$1/(k_{obs})_1 = 1/k_1 + 1/K'k_1 \cdot 1/[NBSC] \quad (6)$$

$$1/(k_{obs})_2 = 1/k_2 + 1/K''k_2 \cdot 1/[NBSC] \quad (7)$$

which were identical with (1), but deduced from equations (4) and (5), respectively

using the experimental $(k_{obs})_1$ and $(k_{obs})_2$ values at different NBSC concentrations at pH 9.40.

Fig. 3. Evaluation of k_1 , k_2 , K' and K'' by graphical method.

The constants A' and B' (equation 1) are, therefore, related to the rate constants (k_1 , k_2) and pre-equilibrium constants (K' , K'') in the manner, $A' = (1/k_1)$ or $(1/k_2)$ and $(A'/B') = K'$ or K'' as the case may be.

Rate constants for the formation of a variety of Ni^{2+} complexes with monodentate and polydentate ligands are found to be close to water exchange rate ($3.2 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$) of Ni^{2+} ¹²⁻¹⁵. Rate constants (k_1 and k_2) for the formation of Ni^{2+} -NBSC complexes are found to be too low (Table 2). Such lower rate of formation of Ni^{2+} complexes were observed ¹⁶ where the uncomplexed ligand could exist in a rigid conformation due to hydrogen bonding, which was quite likely for the uncomplexed LH^- ion. Stabilisation of the carboxylate moiety

of LH^- , due to hydrogen bonding was further evident from the increase of COOH group deprotonation constant (K_{COOH}^H) of NBSC on lowering the temperature ¹. The extent of stabilisation of the carboxylate ion (LH^-) through hydrogen bonding was greater at lower temperature. Positive entropy change accompanying the COOH group deprotonation of the ligand NBSC indicated the formation of chelated structure of the carboxylate anion (LH^-), obviously through hydrogen bonding, involving the carboxylate oxygen atom and the sulphonamido hydrogen atom. Such hydrogen bonded structure of the ligand LH^- ion was probably retained even in the reaction intermediates, viz. $[Intermediate]_1$ and $[Intermediate]_2$ and ruptured in the rate determining steps at the requirement ³ of bidentate (N, S) chelation of Ni^{2+} by the ligand, L^{2-} , ion with release of the thiol proton. These changes could be shown according to Scheme 1. Such a bonding scheme was very much likely for Ni^{2+} , which being a class (b) metal ion would preferentially bind with the softer thiol enl of the ligand to form the intermediates. Closer magnitudes of the successive rate constants (k_1 and k_2) showed that the entry of the second ligand was not at all hindered, in fact, facilitated by the first ligand that was already bonded to the metal ion in the NiL complex. This was due to π -acidity of the sulphur donor atom in the thiol group of the ligand and availability of filled T_{2g} group of orbitals in the Ni^{2+} (d^8) ion, there was possibility of π -electron delocalisation from the Ni^{2+} ion over to the vacant d_{π} orbitals of the thiol sulphur donor atom of the coordinated ligand in the NiL complex through the Ni-S bond. Such Ni-S charge transfer could cause an enhancement of electronegativity of the Ni^{2+} ion in the NiL complex, which then bonded the thiol sulphur donor atom of the second ligand far more easily than the Ni^{2+} (aq) ion. The k_1/k_2 ratio for the present system was close to 5 as against $k_1/k_2 \approx 75$ for the formation of Ni^{2+} -malonato complexes ^{17,18},

Scheme 1. Formation of NiL and NiL_2^{2-} complexes ($R = C_6H_4SO_3$).

where, there was no possibility of π -electron delocation in the metal—ligand bonds. Significantly large values of the pre-equilibrium constants (K' , K'') indicated the existence of metal—ligand interactions stronger than those in outersphere association type in the intermediates and for the same reason as above, the second step pre-equilibrium constant, K'' , was found to be higher than the first step pre-equilibrium constant, K' . This was in agreement with unusual order ($K''_{ML} < K'_{ML_2}$) of the successive formation constants of the Ni^{II} —NBSC complexes found by equilibrium study³.

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